

FEATURES OF DIAGNOSIS OF CHRONIC RHINOSINUSITIS IN CHILDREN WITH CEREBRAL PALSY

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Abstract. Most children with cerebral palsy take anticonvulsant and sedative (hypoinductive) drugs for a long time. As a result, the metabolism of vitamin D in the liver increases, as a result of which hypovitaminosis D develops in the body, which leads to a decrease in calcium absorption in the intestine. Hypocalcemia affects the ossification process, parathyroid function, neuromuscular motility and physiological mechanisms. At the same time, there is an information in the literature that calcium ions play an important role in the movement of floating epithelial cilia. In this study, we studied the dependence of the movement of cilia of ciliated columnar epithelium cells, which perform the mucociliary transport function of the nasal mucosa, on the amount of calcium in the blood. In 158 patients with chronic rhinosinusitis aged from 3 to 16 years (the main group - 98 patients with rhinosinusitis with childhood cerebral palsy, the comparison group - 60 patients with chronic rhinosinusitis), the amount of calcium and 25(OH)D₃ in the blood and the functional activity of the nasal mucosa were checked. According to the results of our study, in patients of the main group compared to the control group, a low level of 25(OH)D₃ in the blood caused a decrease in the amount of calcium (1.8 ± 0.14 mmol/l), which caused a decrease in the mucociliary transport function of the nasal mucosa (30.9 ± 3.65 min). Correlation analysis of the amount of calcium in the blood with 25(OH)D₃ and the amount of calcium in the blood with the time of mucociliary transport in the nasal cavity showed that the nature of binding is correct (+), the binding strength is average (+65).

Keywords: children with cerebral palsy, rhinosinusitis, hypovitaminosis D, hypocalcemia, mucociliary transport.

Relevance. In recent decades, ideas about children with cerebral palsy have been constantly changing, which requires a methodical study of this form of pathology in order to determine the characteristics of the course of the disease in the process of treatment and rehabilitation of patients. It turns out that these various pathologies require the intervention of not only neurologists and orthopedists, but also many other pediatric specialties. The pathology of children with cerebral palsy is often accompanied by disorders of the sensory systems (usually vision and hearing), speech disorders and development disorders of children, symptomatic epilepsy, autonomic disorders, secondary orthopedic problems and other pathological conditions. Many medical practices remain uncertain regarding children born with cerebral palsy. However, children born with cerebral palsy receive limited or no vaccinations. Cerebral palsy is the most common neurological pathology causing disability in patients under 18 years of age. This situation creates a serious risk of contracting infectious diseases. Multidisciplinary and an integrated approach underlie modern ideas about the problem of cerebral palsy in children, adolescents and adults. Therefore, all the latest achievements of modern clinical medicine should be maximally introduced into the daily practice of specialists in various medical fields involved in providing care to patients suffering from this neurological pathology. According to the literature, up to 70% of patients treated for cerebral palsy have a convulsive symptom. This means that they will have to take

anticonvulsant medications for a long time. Long-term use of anticonvulsants leads to the development of hypocalcemia. The amount of calcium in the blood is normally 2.1-2.6 mmol/l, and if it is less than 2.1 mmol/l, then this is hypocalcemia. The causes of hypocalcemia include conditions associated with impaired vitamin D metabolism, conditions associated with pathologies of calcium-sensitive receptors in the cell. Some drugs (convulex, depakine) inhibit the enzyme GABA transaminase during metabolism, and the biotransformation of GABA is blocked. As a result, sodium-potassium ATPase, T-type calcium channels in the cell membrane are partially blocked and the flow of calcium into the cell is reduced. Barbiturates (phenobarbital, benzonal), anticonvulsants are inducers of cytochrome P-450, activate GABA and enhance the metabolism of vitamin D in the liver. Excessive breakdown of vitamin D reduces calcium absorption in the intestine and leads to hypocalcemia. A decrease in the amount of calcium in the blood causes the development of pathological processes in many structures of the body. One of them causes a significant decrease in the movement of floating epithelial cilia.

One of the main protective functions of the nose and paranasal sinuses is the transport function of the mucosal epithelium. Transport of secretion produced from the mucous membrane into the nasopharynx depends on mainly two factors: the motor activity of the cilia of the ciliated epithelium and the liquid or viscous nature of the secretion. The mucous membrane of the nasal cavity acts as a primary protective barrier (barrier) and prevents the penetration of dust particles and various infections from the environment. This protective mechanism involves ciliated columnar epithelium, secretions in the nose and neutrophils, macrophages and immunoglobulins in its contents. The mucous secretion is produced by goblet cells of the nasal mucosa, together with mucus secretion, ciliated epithelial cells form a mucociliary transport system. As a result of the same vibration of the cilia of ciliated epithelial cells, dust particles, microorganisms, and allergens adhere to the mucous secretion and move into the nose and throat, and constant cleanliness is ensured. In the pathogenesis of inflammatory diseases of the nose and paranasal sinuses, the permeability of the blood vessels of the mucosal wall increases, due to this the amount and composition of mucus secretion changes, and mucociliary transport activity is affected to one degree or another. A change in the composition of mucous secretions creates conditions for the growth of pathogenic microorganisms and causes the spread of inflammatory diseases of the nose and paranasal sinuses. The mechanism of separation formation, as well as its control by the body, is currently not fully understood. The mucous membrane of the respiratory tract consists of an indivisible part called the mucociliary system, and is considered the first protective barrier that protects a person from the harmful effects of the environment. The protective function of the ciliated epithelium largely depends on the composition of the mucous secretion. A normal rheological indicator of mucus is the adhesion of inhaled dust particles to the nasopharynx. The average time for this is 10-20 minutes. The functional property of squamous epithelium, along with the composition of mucus, is to prevent the formation of colonies of persistent microflora in a moderate ratio. Normally, the secretion is produced by single-celled goblet cells of the mesocrine type. The normal ratio of packed to ciliated cells is 1:10. Goblet cells are predominantly located in the mucous membrane of the nostrils. The mucous membrane of the nose and paranasal cavities is formed in the same way. The overall separation created by goblet cells is divided into two layers and has a thickness of 8-10 μm . The top layer is a dense gel-like colloidal layer, and the parietal layer is ash, where the cilia are located. Mucus is a semi-solid gel of complex structure that forms a three-dimensional structure based on high molecular weight filamentous polymers, sulfur

bisulfide bridges, hydrogen bonds, van der Waals forces or intercellular forces. According to the chemical composition, the discharge consists of 95% water and, when alkalized, i.e. pH 7.4-7.5, turns into a gel. This change gives the separation fluidity, viscosity and elasticity. The functional activity of the nasal mucosa can be assessed by indicators of mucociliary transport. Therefore, mucociliary clearance tests are the most common objective method for checking the functional state of the nasal mucosa and paranasal cavities. There are many methods for studying the transport activity of ciliated epithelium. Today, the saccharine test is recommended by most researchers as the simplest and most informative method for studying mucociliary transport in the nasal mucosa.

Purpose of the study: to check the mucociliary transport function of the nasal mucosa depending on the amount of calcium in the blood and to determine its clinical effectiveness by adding calcium D3 to complex treatment in patients with acute and chronic paranasal sinusitis with childhood cerebral palsy.

Methods and materials of the study: In the department of pediatric neurology and the advisory clinic of the 1st clinic of Samarkand Medical Institute, over the years of work, 158 patients aged from 3 to 16 years were examined (the main group of 98 patients and the comparison group of 60 patients) and without pathology in the paranasal cavities (control group). In 2019-2021, we examined healthy children consisting of 30 volunteers. Based on the results of an ENT examination (history, complaints, rhinoscopy, pharyngoscopy) and computed tomography examination, various forms of chronic rhinosinusitis were identified in 98 patients with cerebral palsy. All patients underwent a biochemical blood test, the amount of calcium and 25(OH)D3 in the blood was checked, as well as functional indicators of the nasal mucosa. To study mucociliary transport of the nasal mucosa, we used a standard saccharine test. To do this, we injected a piece of saccharine with a diameter of about 1 mm into the region of the mucous membrane of the lower part of the nasal cavity, approximately 1 cm behind its anterior end, and counted the time until a sweet taste was felt in the subject's mouth using a stopwatch. During the examination, the patient was explained that he should not swallow, sneeze, blow his nose, or breathe quickly through the nose, and was advised to swallow once a minute. The examination was carried out taking into account the inability to bleed the mucous membrane or inject drugs into the nasal cavity. Normal values for saccharine time vary widely. If the subject did not feel a sweet taste in his mouth after the specified time, we repeated the test to determine whether he could taste the saccharine. We also used endoscopic broom blue injection to confirm the diagnosis of mucociliary dysfunction in all patients.

To determine the hydrogen index (pH) of nasal mucus, we used special indicator paper. In this case, we inserted indicator paper directly into the accumulated mucous discharge in the nasal cavity, without touching the mucous membrane as much as possible, and after some time the changed color of the paper was compared with a special standard. Using this method, we determined the hydrogen index in all patients and healthy individuals. According to many literary sources, normal nasal mucus has a slightly alkaline reaction, the average pH is 7.015 ± 0.007 . The concentration of hydrogen ions in the nasal mucus changes for various reasons, its change to one degree or another affects the physiological functions of the nasal mucosa (the frequency and strength of vibration of the epithelial cilia of the mucous membrane, the viability of cell cilia, the activity of the enzyme lysozyme, which is involved in the protection of nasal mucus).

The study of the absorption and secretory functions of the nasal mucosa allows us to assess the state of blood supply to the nasal mucosa, the functioning and permeability of the serous and

mucous glands. The activity of these functions of the nasal mucosa is ensured by the autonomic nervous system. Many factors influencing the autonomic system, to one degree or another, affect the absorption and secretory functions of the nasal mucosa. For example: warming or cooling of air temperature, increase or decrease in the concentration of hydrogen ions in nasal mucus, etc.

In our study, we used the method recommended by B. M. Sagalovich to determine the absorption function of the nasal mucosa. The essence of the method is that gauze soaked in a 1% atropine solution is systemically introduced into the middle nasal pathway for 15 minutes and assessed by the reaction time of pupil dilation. As you know, the nasal septum is formed from mucous glands and goblet cells, as well as from the lymphatic system located in the nasal mucosa. Breathable air obtained with the help of nasal mucus is cleared of particles, humidified and supplied to the next section of the respiratory system, and the contents of nasal mucus are neutralized from microbes using the enzyme lysozyme. Therefore, in our study we studied precisely this function of the mucous membrane of the brown cavity. For the study, the separation function of the nasal mucosa was determined using the method of Shigabutdinov U.Kh. For this purpose, cotton balls weighing 25 mg were first weighed on a torsion balance. During the procedure, cotton balls were inserted into the nasal cavity in the middle of the lower part of the nasal septum for 1 minute, then the cotton swab was removed and weighed again on a torsion scale, and the results were recorded. A study of the absorption and secretory functions of the nasal mucosa was carried out with a difference of 1 day.

Table 1

Results of testing the functional activity of the nasal mucosa in patients

Indicators	The main group n=98	Comparison group n=60	Control group n=30
Indicators of mucociliary clearance of the nasal cavity (in a minute)	30,9±3,65	25,14±3,20	11,16±2,24
Hydrogen ion concentration (pH) in the nasal cavity	7,33±0,06	7,33±0,08	7,11±0,06
Absorption function of the mucous membrane (mydriasis time) (min)	76,92±2,78	77,92±3,75	65,42±2,32
Secretory function of the mucous membrane weight (mg)	47,62±3,49	48,27±3,56	37,1±1,87

*p≤0.05 compared to the control group; *p≤0.05 between groups.

According to the examination results, the transport function of the nasal mucosa in patients of the main group averaged 30.90±3.65, the transport function of the nasal mucosa in patients of the comparison group averaged 25.14±3.20, and the transport function of the nasal mucosa in the control group group averaged 11.16±2.24 (Table 1). In healthy children in the control group, the time from the introduction of saccharin into the nasal cavity until the appearance of a sweet taste in the mouth ranged from 5 to 19 minutes.

During the examination, the average pH in the nasal cavity in patients with rhinosinusitis was 7.33±0.06 in the main group, 7.33±0.08 in the comparison group, 7.11±0.06 in the control

group; the nasal suction function index (pupil dilation time) averaged 76.42 ± 2.8 in the main group, 77.88 ± 3.97 in the comparison group and 65.20 ± 2.20 in the control group; The nasal septum function index (weight, mg) in the main group averaged 47.62 ± 3.49 , in the comparison group - 48.27 ± 3.56 , in the control group - 37.10 ± 1.87 (Table 1). Compared with the control group and between groups, all indicators were $p < 0.05$.

It should be noted that most patients with cerebral palsy constantly take neurological (anticonvulsant, sedative, diuretic) drugs. One of the characteristic properties of these drugs (hypovitaminosis D due to hepatoinductive action) causes a decrease in the amount of calcium in the body. Calcium, in turn, is one of the main factors in the movement of floating epithelium in the body. Research has proven that reducing the amount of calcium in the body weakens the movement of the floating epithelium.

Therefore, in our study, we investigated the level of calcium in the blood and its effect on the transport function of the nasal mucosa.

In addition to determining the functional parameters of the nasal mucosa, the level of calcium in the blood and 25(OH)D₃ was also determined. According to it, the main group of patients had a blood calcium level of 1.80 ± 0.14 , a 25(OH)D₃ level - 15.9 ± 3.3 , a comparison group of patients with a blood calcium level of 2.08 ± 0.17 - 25(OH). The amount of D₃ was 24.9 ± 3.3 , and in the control group the amount of calcium in the blood was 2.28 ± 0.16 , 25(OH)D₃ - 30.5 ± 3.8 (Table 2).

Table 2

Biochemical analysis	The main group n=98	Comparison group n=60	Control group n=30
The amount of calcium in the blood mmol/l	$1,8 \pm 0,14$	$2,08 \pm 0,17$	$2,28 \pm 0,16$
25(OH)D ₃ (mg/ml)	$15,9 \pm 3,3$	$24,9 \pm 3,3$	$30,5 \pm 3,8$

Based on the above data, the lower level of 25(OH)D₃ in the blood of patients in the main group than in the control group was due to a decrease in the amount of calcium (1.8 ± 0.14 mmol/l) and this caused a decrease in the mucociliary transport function of the nasal mucosa (30.9 ± 3.65 min). Correlation analysis of the level of calcium in the blood with 25(OH)D₃ and the time of mucociliary transport of the nasal mucosa showed the correct (+) nature of binding and average binding strength (+65).

Conclusion. Most patients with cerebral palsy take anticonvulsants and sedatives for a long time. This, due to the hepatoinductive action of this group of drugs, accelerates the metabolism of vitamin D in the body and leads to a decrease in its amount. As a result, the absorption of calcium from the intestine into the blood decreases and hypocalcemia develops. A decrease in the amount of calcium in the blood leads to a decrease in the force of movement and vibration of the cilia, which causes a slowdown in mucociliary transport. As a result, the functional state of the nasal mucosa deteriorates and leads to a prolongation of the course of inflammatory diseases of the nose and nasal cavity.

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